

Silent Bullying and Quiet Firing

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An *old-school* mobbing, which is overt enough to trigger immediate or delayed legal action against the bully, seems to be replaced by new covert methods of bullying at work, which are so sophisticated that a victim's testimony might sound completely crazy. There are two relatively new terms, which almost sound like a myth, and these are *silent bullying* and *quiet firing*.

There is not much available scientific literature on this issue, which means that there is no or little interest in the scientific community for what seems to be a new method of getting rid of unwanted individuals from workplaces. The so-called *silent bully* is described as a leader (boss) that is using a condescending and usually voiceless type of behavior, that is usually repetitive in nature, causing emotional trauma to a targeted individual or a group of people^{1,2}. Such behavior might be particularly detrimental if it is consciously directed only towards one employee, while other employees get different, better treatment. In such cases, this sophisticated form of gaslighting and mobbing might cause accumulating psychological (micro)damage to the victim while making it impossible for the victim to

seek legal protection, as there is no or little evidence of mobbing. The only possible way out of this situation for the victim would be to simply quit their job, which, on the other hand, imposes an existential threat for the victim (unemployment, poverty, homelessness).

Quiet firing is described as a method ranging from the manager's (intentional) failure to adequately provide coaching, support, and career development to an employee up to the manager causing an employee to experience truly toxic and miserable working conditions, which is a form of gaslighting³. The manager (leader, boss) who wants to simply *squeeze out* an employee from the team might use silent bullying methods instead of being overtly unjust toward the targeted individual. Signs of quiet firing mentioned in the available literature are:

- The targeted individual is being overly-criticized.
- The targeted individual is not being invited to meetings and events (social and professional isolation).
- A targeted individual is being deprived of critical information needed for a particular task or project, making it impossible to meet professional standards.

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- The targeted individual is not included in the career development plans and discussions.
- The targeted individual is not getting raises, bonuses, or promotions⁴.

It seems that silent bullying and quiet firing are effective ways to turn the blade of guilt and responsibility from the perpetrator to the victim, and every attempt by the victim to seek justice and to testify might be simply discarded as paranoid delusion. Although the warning signs of quiet firing, such as reassigning important job responsibilities to other employees, demoting an employee, not assigning promising new opportunities, or setting up unreasonable performance targets⁵, might seem to be noticeable, I think that it might be actually very hard to prove that such misbehavior of a leader is truly a form of mobbing and that it is not the victim's fault. The silent bully might defend their misbehavior using sophisticated slander so that the victim appears to be irrational, conflicting, emotionally unstable, and incompetent.

If other employees are getting better treatment, there is a possibility that others will simply testify in favor of silent bully in a legal proceeding. Even documenting the factual destructive behavior of a leader might be discarded as irrelevant as long as the team

is functional; one person's misery might not be taken into account in the context of corporative capitalism and profit.

In order to prevent silent bullying and quiet firing, systemic changes might be necessary, such as reducing the power and wealth of the ruling elite, tackling corruption effectively, increasing awareness about the problem, empowering workers' rights (for all, not just the rich), and increasing the availability of legal protection for everyone.

REFERENCES

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